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Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti erkin tadqiqotchisi

BADIIY TARJIMADA LINGVOMADANIY TAHLILNING AHAMIYATI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6777120>**ANNOTATSIYA**

Jahon tarjimashunosligida turli badiiy asarlarni qiyosiy tadqiq qilish tobora jadallashib bormoqda. Ma'lumki, tarjima inson faoliyatining eng qadimiy turlaridan biri bo'lib, u tufayli biz jamiyat taraqqiyoti tarixining barcha tafsilotlarini ochiq-oydin tasavvur etamiz. Tarjima xalqaro do'stlik, qardoshlik va hamkorlik manfaatlariga, xalqlar o'rtasidagi iqtisodiy-siyosiy, ilmiy, madaniy va adabiy aloqalarning kengayishiga xizmat qiluvchi qudratli quroldir. U turli xalqlar adabiyotlarining o'zaro aloqasi va bir-biriga ta'siri jarayonini tezlashtiradi. Tarjima asarlari tufayli kitobxonlar jahon adabiyoti durdonalaridan bahramand bo'ladi. Shu bilan birga, tarjima tillarning rivojlanish sur'atini jadallashtiruvchi, lug'at boyligini oshiruvchi va takomillashtiruvchi vosita sifatida ham muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ushbu maqola, badiiy tarjimada lingvomadaniy tahlilning ahamiyati masalasini o'rganadi, hamda tarjima ilmi masalasi yuzasidan fikrlar tahlil qilinadi. Zero, tarjima ilmini tahlil va tadqiq etish, mohir tarjimonlar tajribalarini umumlashtirish, yangi va yanada mukammalroq tarjimalar o'tmishdan to hozirgacha bo'lgan holatini o'rganish dolzarb masaladir.

Tayanch so'zlar: badiiy matn, milliy kolorit, tarjima, tarjima ilmi, tahlil.

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**ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО АНАЛИЗА В
ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОМ ПЕРЕВОДЕ****АННОТАЦИЯ**

В мировом переводоведении набирает обороты сравнительное изучение различных произведений искусства. Общеизвестно, что перевод — одна из древнейших форм человеческой деятельности, благодаря которой мы можем отчетливо представить себе все подробности истории общественного развития. Перевод является мощным оружием в интересах межнациональной дружбы, братства и сотрудничества, а также расширения экономических, политических, научных, культурных и литературных связей между народами. Он ускоряет процесс взаимодействия и взаимодействия между литературами разных народов. Благодаря переведенным произведениям читатели наслаждаются шедеврами мировой литературы. В то же время перевод является важным средством ускорения развития языков, увеличения и улучшения богатства словарного запаса. В данной статье анализируется наука перевода и его проблемы. Так как ни одна наука не может существовать без учета и использования опыта прошлого, работ предшественников в соответствующей области, то в первую очередь необходимо использование и обобщение данных истории перевода и

переводческой мысли, подведение известного итога борьбы взглядов и мнений по вопросам перевода.

Ключевые слова: художественный текст, национальный колорит, перевод, переводоведение, анализ.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF LINGUACULTURAL ANALYSIS IN LITERARY TRANSLATION

ANNOTATION

In world translation studies, the comparative study of various works of art is gaining momentum. It is well known that translation is one of the most ancient forms of human activity, thanks to which we can clearly imagine all the details of the history of social development. Translation is a powerful weapon in the interests of international friendship, brotherhood and cooperation, as well as the expansion of economic, political, scientific, cultural and literary ties between nations. It accelerates the process of interaction and interaction between the literatures of different peoples. Thanks to the translated works, readers will enjoy the masterpieces of world literature. At the same time, translation is an important tool for accelerating the development of languages, increasing and improving the richness of vocabulary. This article analyzes the science of translation and its problems. Since no science can exist without taking into account and using the experience of the past, the work of predecessors in the relevant field, it is first necessary to use and generalize the data of the history of translation and translation thought, summing up the well-known result of the struggle of views and opinions on translation issues.

Key words: literary text, national flavor, translation, translation studies, analysis.

In addition to the specific issues of translation theory and practice, research in the field of translation studies in the world is conducting extensive research on general issues that reflect the essence of the field, and the issue of translation is becoming more and more attractive to researchers. Speaking of the science of music, and having in mind not only the study of the physical aspects of musical sounds, but also the understanding of the structures that these sounds enter into in various types of musical composition, no one underestimates the importance of skill in composing music and the art found in its good interpretation. . The same is certainly true of translation.

The science of translation is only one side of linguistic science, which in turn is only one of the behavioral sciences, the purpose of which is to carefully describe the role of verbal communication in human behavior. However, the analysis of translation does differ from most linguistic studies in that in translation we deal with at least two languages and study them in terms of rendering formally different means of the same content.

In our country, especially in the process of building a new Uzbekistan, comprehensive measures are being taken to further develop the Uzbek language and improve language policy. One of the urgent tasks is to "preserve the purity of the state language, enrich it and improve the speech culture of the population." In this regard, the comparative study of the linguacultural features of the use of barbarisms in linguistics in the context of multilingualism in the English and Uzbek languages, the enrichment of the Uzbek lexicon with new elements, the expansion of non-standard acquisitions and the importance.

In the science of translation, contextual meanings are of particular importance. Contextual meanings arise in the process of using words in speech, depending on the environment, and are realized under the influence of a narrow, wide and extralinguistic context.

A word, especially a polysemantic one, is a complex semantic structure. The main thing in it is the nominative meaning, directly aimed at objects and phenomena of reality.

This, according to V.V. Vinogradov, "the support and socially conscious foundation of all its other meanings and applications." The problem of the hierarchy of the meanings of a polysemantic

word is devoted to a number of studies, among which, first of all, the works of R.O. Jakobson about the main, main and particular meanings and E. Kurilovich about primary and secondary semantic functions. The difference between the main linguistic meaning and private meanings hierarchically subordinate to it lies in the fact that the main meaning is one that is not determined by the context, while the remaining (private) meanings add context elements to the semantically elements of the main meaning. The enrichment of the context leads to the emergence of further private shades of private values [1].

Отношения тапа «главное значение – частное значение» являются регулярными в многозначных словах, что представляет одну из важнейших характеристик полисемии. А.И. Смирницкий подчёркивал, что «связи между лексико-семантическими вариантами в системе языка оказываются повторяющимися, типичными, закономерными. Главное значение и частные значения, непосредственно данные в регулярно реализуемых позициях, относятся к собственно языковым (как и их семантический вариант – общее значение) [2].

According to the degree of frequency, one can distinguish between ordinary (repeating) and occasional (random, individual) contextual meanings. The first over time, with the accumulation of observations, pass into the category of variant correspondences. The latter can appear and disappear as a manifestation of the subjective use of words by one or another author and are most often found in fiction. "The transformation of the "occasional" use of the word into the usual" is one of the most frequent ways of developing polysemy. X. Cassares gives a number of reasons that prompt the speaker to discard "the generally accepted word that is spinning on his tongue" and replace it with another "used in an unusual meaning for him." This is mainly a sudden association of ideas, emotional excitement (obviously, a state of passion), the desire for expressive richness, to achieve a comic effect, or simply a desire to attract the attention of the listener or reader. It is the occasional, unusual use of the word and the reasons for this that must be taken into account by the translator.

Contextual meanings are not introduced from the outside, but are the realization of the meanings potentially embedded in the word. This can be established from the semantic structure of the word.

The definition of the lexical meaning of a word through the disclosure of its semantic structure as a system of bilateral minimal lexical units - lexico-semantic variants of the word allows us to take into account such factors that usually escape the researcher's field of vision that determine the lexical meaning, such as: 1) socially conscious and settled (systemic) contexts of the use of the word ; 2) belonging of a given word to a certain semantic or lexical-grammatical category of words; 3) specific lexical connections with other words, due to the models of semantic compatibility of verbal signs inherent in this language; 4) semantic correlations of words with synonyms and other similar words in the language system as a whole.

The above definition, given by A.A. Ufimtseva, contains a list of factors that determine the characteristics of the word as the basic unit of the language, fixed by the vocabulary, and as the minimum unit of the speech flow.

As mentioned above, a polysemantic word is a complex semantic structure. Its main meaning is the nominative meaning. The "primary function", writes E. Kurilovich, coincides with the "principal value" of Jakobson, the "secondary functions" are identical with other "private values". The use of the expressions "proper (literal) and figurative meaning" according to E. Kurilovich suggests a certain hierarchy between them. "It is clear," he continues, that the immediate data are the "private" meanings that appear in specific conditions (in context).

The principal meaning and particular meanings directly given in regularly realized positions are proper linguistic ones (as well as their semantic invariant – common meaning). Beyond regularity are chains of "further particular shades of particular meanings" (E. Kurilovich), "applications" of the word (V.V. Vinogradov), word meanings that already have an extralinguistic character (V.A. Zvegintsev, G.P. Melnikov and others). These are the contextual meanings of the word, the special "applications" of the word in the context, which go beyond the usual linguistic meanings, although they are indirectly motivated by linguistic meanings through a system of "hidden" internal forms, implications. Such contextual meanings (actual meanings, in the terminology of W. Schmidt) are not

fixed in explanatory dictionaries as going beyond the limits of the usage and not revealing regular relationships. A.R. Luria emphasized that the meaning, in contrast to the usual linguistic meaning, is the actualization of “those aspects that are associated with a given situation and the affective attitude of the subject”, “transformation of meanings, selection from among all the connections behind the word, that system of connections which is relevant at the moment. It is easy to understand that the word rope for a person who wants to pack a purchase has one meaning, but for a person who has fallen into a hole and wants to get out of it, this is a means of salvation.

All this creates a prerequisite for distinguishing between the actual linguistic and extralinguistic content of the word: the meaning of the word (main, private) ~ the meaning of the word.

Such an opposition is based on the opposition of regular and irregular relations of meanings in words or otherwise - meanings with explicit and implicit internal forms. Using the well-known position of A.A. Potebnya that in word formation in the circle of words of one root, any previous one can be called the internal form of the subsequent one, it can be argued that in semantic derivation (the structure of a polysemantic word) each topologically previous one, in a way of representing its extralinguistic content .

The meaning of a word as an extralinguistic use of a sign is based on modification, contextual expansion of the original internal form, its actual concretization. The contextual internal form is determined not only by the specifics of a given linguistic text, but also by the system of extralinguistic knowledge, the actual cognitive orientation of a person's speech and thinking activity, the theory of knowledge - epistemology. The sign and its meaning, thanks to such a mobile internal form, which occupies an intermediate position between language and reality (including poetically modeled), receive a specific reference in the text, usually “displaced” in comparison with the usus. Such a contextual internal form, unlike the usual one, could be called a linguistic episystem.

In semiotic terms, the opposition between “meaning of the word” (“internal form”) and “meaning of the word” (“linguo-episystem”) finds justification in the distinction between semantics, which studies the relationship between sign and meaning, and stigmatism, which considers the relationship between sign and object, proposed by G. Klaus. , which operate respectively with the concepts of “usual (linguistic) meaning” and “actual (extra-linguistic) meaning”.

The concept of “meaning” thus turns out to be inextricably linked with epistemological semantics, which goes beyond the limits of proper linguistic, with the general theory of reference. The opposition “meaning of the word” - “meaning of the word” is not rigid, it involves transitional cases, while the meaning itself turns out to be connected with the meaning by a system of motivations, an implication, supported by extralinguistic data.

The nature and types of a linguistic episystem can be varied: the meaning of a word that determines it is determined both by its original meaning and the specifics of the text, and by factors of an extralinguistic nature (the subject-conceptual structure of reality itself).

Literature has always acted as a moral censor that does not allow the world to plunge into the abyss of lack of spirituality. In the technocratic and automated society that we have today, the importance of literature increases many times over. Humanity, no matter what language its individual representatives speak, addresses its reflections to everyone without exception. The noble task of introducing everyone and everyone to the results of the work of thought of this elite is served by literary translation - the most important means of intercultural exchange, bringing peoples and civilizations together.

It is difficult to point to any phenomenon in literary criticism regarding which there would be such a huge number of polar points of view as the problem of literary translation. Being a particular type of translation, it is fundamentally different from all others in the specifics of its subject and the range of issues raised. Which translation is correct: literal or free; the translator must be a “shadow” of the author of the original or has the right to be creative in the translation; what language the translation should be written in: how the author himself would write if the language of the translation was native to him, or the language in which it is clearly felt to “take it into account”; what is more important: an orientation towards preserving and transmitting the features of the literature from which

the work is translated or ensuring that the translation complies with the norms and traditions of the perceiving literature; translation is a copy of the original or a new work of art; is it possible to achieve absolute adequacy of the original in the translation, if not, what translation can be considered adequate? - this is the range of topical issues that every translator or theorist inevitably faces. Naturally, there can be no definitive answers to them, since creativity (and literary translation, of course, is a creative matter) involves a constant search for new ways and solutions.

Literary translation in its development went through phases of rapid growth of interest in itself and its weakening, in its development the movement "in depth" was replaced by the movement "in breadth". The current period can be characterized as a movement "in depth": due to the widespread bilingualism and polylingualism, the demands on the quality of translated works are increasing. The reader is not satisfied with the transfer of the general content of the original, he requires reflection in the translation of the poetics of the author, the stylistic features of the work. In this regard, the demand for translation criticism is also growing, since "criticism is always associated with understanding the essence of a phenomenon."

A lot of research has been devoted to the problems of literary translation in Uzbek and foreign translation studies, which indicates the versatility of this phenomenon, the inexhaustibility of its problems. Within the framework of these works, a significant layer is made up of studies devoted to the transfer of national color in literary translation has become especially relevant in recent times. In literary criticism, it appears under various terms and (national form, national coloring, national identity, local color, historical color, color of the era, national color).

A. Fedorov's book "On Literary Translation" is a major contribution to the theory of translation. It highlights the main theoretical provisions of literary translation. A. Fedorov also touches upon the issue of national color and its transmission. Dwelling on the tasks facing critics, he writes: "Neither lapses nor curiosities should be the focus of criticism. They are secondary. They can also be found in good translations, and their absence is by no means equivalent to the high quality of the translator's work. The main requirement for translation, according to the researcher, is "to preserve the originality of the original, so that it does not depreciate." Quite rightly, A. Fedorov speaks out against translators who preserved proverbs, sayings, idioms in translation, "the national specificity of which consists not only in the native Russian character of words, but also in the mention of specially Russian realities ("I need to make you eat kalachi", "Don't bast of shit", "Go to Tula with your samovar", "Scream all over Ivanovskaya", "Moscow was not built in one day", etc.). He emphasizes that such "Russianisms contradict the real-factual content of the translated work, its national background" [3].

Two articles by V. Rossels [4] are devoted to the problem of conveying national color in literary translation, who was one of the first researchers to deeply and comprehensively shed light on this issue. In his articles, a sufficiently complete and substantiated description of the concept of national color is given, its components are clarified, and the methods and principles of their reproduction in literary translation are outlined.

The national color can be considered a set of characteristic features of any nation, nationality, its originality, reflected in works of art. In this regard, local color is the characteristic features of a given area, [5] the color of an era, or historical color is the characteristic features of a particular period in the history of a people. Consequently, the local color and the color of the era are components of the national color.

National color is a very broad concept. It covers the peculiar national characteristics of the people, their history and life.

A nation is a historically formed community of people, which is characterized by the unity of the material conditions of life. Each nation has its own territory, its own economy and culture, its own language, its own mental warehouse. By the latter, we understand the national character, which is formed during the centuries-old labor and creative activity of people, national traditions, customs, beliefs, prejudices, feelings and tastes, interests and views. The peculiarity of the spiritual life of a particular nation, reflected in architecture, fine and applied arts, choreography, music, literature, gives any kind of art a unique national flavor [6].

The dispute about the impossibility of conveying the national color in literary translation, which has not subsided for several centuries in a row, in our opinion, is primarily due to inaccurate translations. Practice shows that it is possible to translate all texts while preserving all the features of the original and the culture of this nation, and sometimes the translation is not inferior to the original, and in other cases even surpasses it. The main thing is to find the key to the translated work, which will allow to overcome the translation difficulties that arise in the process of reexpressing the work into another language, with minimal loss to the ideological and content basis of the original text.

So the national flavor has its limits, since ethnically determined differences in extralinguistic experience and the presence of a very bright cultural component in words in some cases represent almost insurmountable obstacles to achieving an equivalent translation.

In the process of translation, part of the cultural information is lost. This is normal to the extent that the loss of some information within certain (insignificant) limits is a phenomenon inherent in translation, however, losses beyond this measure, the leveling of national and cultural specifics make an equivalent translation impossible. In this case, they resort to retelling, adaptive arrangement, etc.

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